

THE INVESTIGATION INTO THE DEPENDENCY LEVEL OF TURKISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS ON COURSEBOOKS

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Abstract:

Coursebooks are one of the basic materials used in educational environments. So, it is crucial to determine teachers' attitudes toward coursebooks and the degree they depend on them. Based on this, this study examines Turkish Language teachers' coursebook dependency and shows how this dependency varies according to their genders, schools, levels of education, and years of experience. The study uses a descriptive survey carried out with a quantitative approach. The sample of the study consists of 53 Turkish Language teachers determined by simple random sampling. The data of the study were collected employing the scale named "Dependency Scale of Turkish Language Teachers on Coursebooks". The data were analyzed using the arithmetic mean, t-test, and ANOVA test, which are descriptive analysis techniques. As a result, it is seen that teachers are moderately dependent on coursebooks and that their genders, schools, levels of education, and years of experience do not have any effect on their coursebook dependency. However, it is seen that there is a significant difference in the sub-dimension "obligations/advantages" in favor of males, and there is a significant difference in the sub-dimension "school type" in favor of teachers working in private schools.

Keywords: Turkish Language teaching, Turkish Language teachers, coursebook, coursebook dependency

1. Introduction

During the teaching process in which students acquire target skills, written, visual, auditory or both written, visual and auditory tools are used. Among these tools, the coursebooks are the most used ones. Coursebooks have been one of the most important factors of the teaching process since the first half of the 19th century when compulsory

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education began to appear in Western Europe (Demircioglu, 2013, p. 120). Similarly, it can be stated that they are used as basic material for all levels of national education.

There are some benefits that coursebooks offer to all stakeholders in teaching activities. Namely, "*they ensure that the activities in teaching process are carried out in an orderly manner*" (Gocer, 2008, p. 197), and they present the learning outcomes in the curriculum to students in a comprehensive and planned manner. They also enable students in different parts of a country to go through similar processes in terms of curriculum, learning contents and activities, and evaluation.

Turkish coursebooks are the books that include different types of written texts supported with visual texts, which aim to help students acquire basic language skills through activities suitable for their development. They also provide teachers with rich content that they can use in their lessons and enable students to follow the course interactively. Besides, thanks to coursebooks, teachers find the texts to be used in the course without any planning, activities, and studies related to these texts as well.

Turkish coursebooks are the primary materials used in teaching Turkish as a mother tongue (Ozbay, 2003, p. 63). In this regard, coursebooks should be prepared following the principles and learning outcomes in the curriculum, the activities should be designed inclusively, considering the individual differences, and the format features should be created according to the class level. The current status of Turkish coursebooks according to the mentioned issues should be demonstrated through different studies. Many studies have already been carried out for this purpose. In these studies, coursebooks are evaluated according to teachers' views (Kolac, 2003; Akkaya and Susar Kirmizi, 2007; Epcacan and Okcu, 2010; Sahin, 2010; Ceran, 2015; Cin Seker, 2018), the texts in coursebooks are examined in terms of readability and textuality criteria (Zorbaz, 2007; Mert, 2011; Aydin, 2012; Bagci and Unal, 2013; Bas and Inan Yildiz, 2015; Cin, 2015; Cin Seker, 2019), and coursebooks are analyzed in terms of vocabulary based on both activity and text (Pehlivan, 2003; Aslan, 2006; Karadag and Kurudayioglu, 2010; Turhan, 2010). Besides, Kutlu (1999) examines coursebooks in terms of the comprehension questions in the books, Bas (2003) examines the text types in the coursebooks, Diliduzgun (2004) examines children's literature in coursebooks, Iseri (2007) examines the suitability of the coursebooks for curriculum objectives, Gocer (2008) examines the activities in the coursebooks in terms of assessment and evaluation, and Karagoz and Aksoy Ada (2018) examine the texts in the coursebooks in terms of genre, theme, and originality. There are also studies that examine coursebooks in terms of values education (Parlakyildiz, 2009; Karagoz and 2009; Firat and Mocan, 2014; Susar Kirmizi, 2014; Capoglu and Okur, 2015; Padem and Aktan, 2016; Pilav & Erdogan, 2016; Gul, 2017; Kaskaya and Duran, 2017).

When the literature is evaluated broadly, it is understood that the focus of the studies is the quality of Turkish coursebooks. However, no study is found to determine the Turkish Language teachers' coursebook dependency level. This study aims to determine Turkish Language teachers' views on using coursebooks and their dependency on them. With this aspect, the study is thought to contribute to the literature.

So, the study answers the question “At what level is Turkish Language teachers’ coursebook dependency?”

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

The study is descriptive survey research carried out with a quantitative approach. Survey research is “*research that is carried out on relatively larger samples compared to other studies, where participants’ opinions about a subject or event or their characteristics such as interest, skill, ability, and attitude are determined.*” (Buyukozturk, Kilic Cakmak, Akgun, Karadeniz & Demirel, 2014, p. 177). Since the study aims to determine Turkish Language teachers’ views on coursebook dependency, the survey *research design is chosen.*

2.2 Population and Sample

The population of the study is Turkish Language teachers working in secondary schools affiliated to Tokat Provincial Directorate of National Education. The sample of the study consists of 53 Turkish Language teachers selected from the universe with simple random sampling. In simple random sampling, every individual or object in the universe has the chance to be selected equally (Akarsu, 2015, p. 34). 28 of the teachers in the sample are females and 25 are males; 47 of them are undergraduates and 6 are graduates. 34 of the teachers work in state schools and 19 in private schools; 11 of them have 1-5 years, 16 of them have 6-10 years, 13 of them have 11-15 years, 11 of them have 16-20 years, and 2 of them have over 20 years of experience.

2.3 Data Collection Tool

The data of the study were collected employing the “Dependency Scale of Turkish Language Teachers on Coursebooks” developed by Ozturk and Cerci (2019). The scale is a 5-point Likert type. It consists of four sub-dimensions and a total of 21 items. In their study, Ozturk and Cerci (2019) determine the Cronbach’s Alpha value of the scale as 0,981 for the overall scale. In this study, the overall reliability coefficient of the scale was calculated as 0.745. The fact that Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient is between 0.60 and 0.80 shows that the scale is very reliable (Field 2000, as cited in Metin 2015, p. 189). The analysis results for the reliability coefficient seem consistent with each other. The fact that the calculated reliability coefficient value is high indicates that the data were collected with a highly reliable tool.

2.4 Data Analysis

To analyze the data, especially along with the arithmetic mean, which is a descriptive analysis technique; t-test and ANOVA test were used to determine the relationship between the variables gender, school type, level of education, and years of experience. The data were evaluated according to the 95% confidence interval.

3. Findings

This part of the study first presents the items in the scale and the averages of the sub-dimensions according to the variables gender, school type and level of education. Then, it provides information about whether Turkish Language teachers' coursebook dependency varies according to their genders, schools, level of education, and years of experience.

Table 1: The Data Showing the Turkish Language Teachers' Genders, Schools and Level of Education Regarding Their Coursebook Dependency

The Sub-Dimensions and Items	The Averages According to Variables					
	Gender		School Type		Level of Education	
	Female	Male	Private School	State School	Undergraduate	Graduate
1. I do not depend on coursebooks as the texts in them are too long.*	3,82	3,28	4,00	3,32	3,48	4,16
2. As I can prepare better activities than the ones in coursebooks, I do not depend on coursebooks.*	2,85	3,16	2,36	3,35	3,08	2,33
3. I do not depend on coursebooks as they hinder the development of students' mental skills.*	3,60	3,44	3,52	3,52	3,57	3,16
4. I depend on coursebooks as the texts in them trigger the creativity of the students.	2,75	2,96	2,78	2,88	2,93	2,16
5. As the activities in coursebooks are of good quality, I depend on them.	2,78	3,00	2,57	3,05	2,91	2,66
6. As I use better texts than the ones in coursebooks, I do not depend on them.	2,89	2,84	2,05	3,32	2,91	2,50
7. As coursebooks improve students' basic skills, I depend on them.	2,96	3,32	3,05	3,17	3,14	3,00
8. I think that my dependency on coursebooks affects my creativity negatively.*	2,89	2,92	3,15	2,76	2,91	2,83
Total	24,57	24,92	23,52	25,41	24,97	22,83
Average	3,07	3,11	2,94	3,17	3,12	2,85

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Obligations	9. As coursebooks are approved by the Board of Education, I prefer to depend on them.	3,28	4,00	3,57	3,64	3,59	3,83
	10. As coursebooks are prepared according to the thematic approach, I depend on them.	3,35	3,64	3,52	3,47	3,57	2,83
	11. I use coursebooks as they save from the burden of making an annual lesson plan.	2,89	3,04	3,00	2,94	2,97	2,83
	12. As I have a lot of classes to teach, I depend on coursebooks.	2,10	2,52	2,00	2,47	2,36	1,83
Total	11,64	13,20	12,10	12,52	12,51	11,33	
Average	2,91	3,30	3,02	3,13	3,12	2,95	
Activities	13. I have my students do the listening activities in the student's workbook.	4,07	4,04	4,26	3,94	4,02	4,33
	14. I have my students do the grammar activities in the student's workbook.	4,50	4,44	4,68	4,35	4,44	4,66
	15. I have my students do the writing activities in the student's workbook.	4,17	4,00	4,47	3,88	4,06	4,33
	16. I have my students do the reading activities in the student's workbook.	4,50	4,04	4,63	4,08	4,23	4,66
	17. I have my students do the speaking activities in the student's workbook.	4,10	4,00	4,57	3,76	4,06	4,00
Total	21,35	20,52	22,63	20,02	20,82	22,00	
Average	4,27	4,10	4,52	4,00	4,16	4,40	
Teacher's Competence	18. As my subject matter knowledge is not enough, I depend on coursebooks.	1,53	1,52	1,31	1,64	1,59	1,00
	19. As my knowledge of teaching methods is not enough, I depend on coursebooks.	1,60	1,52	1,36	1,67	1,61	1,16
	20. I depend on coursebooks as I cannot prepare activities for students' interests/curiosity/levels.	1,82	1,76	1,47	1,97	1,85	1,33
	21. As I do not know about the process of preparing an activity, I depend on coursebooks.	1,82	1,68	1,42	1,94	1,78	1,50

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Total	6,78	6,48	5,57	7,23	6,85	5,00
Average	1,69	1,62	1,39	1,80	1,71	1,25
The Overall Total	64,35	65,12	63,84	65,20	65,17	61,16

According to Table 1, the female teachers' score is 64.35, and male teachers' is 65.12. While the total score of the teachers working in the private school is 63.84, the score of those working in public school is 65.20. The score of teachers with an undergraduate degree is 65.17, while the score of teachers with a graduate degree is 61.16. Table 2 presents data on whether the total score the teachers have varies according to their genders.

Table 2: t-Test Results According to the Variable Gender

Sub-Dimension	Gender	N	Average	ss	t	p<0,05
Limitations	Female	28	24,57	5,80	-,256	,799
	Male	25	24,92	4,03		
Obligations	Female	28	11,64	3,18	-2,015	,049
	Male	25	13,20	2,30		
Activities	Female	28	21,35	3,29	,803	,426
	Male	25	20,52	4,28		
Teacher's Competence	Female	28	6,78	3,78	,322	,749
	Male	25	6,48	3,04		
Total	Female	28	64,35	9,59	-,317	,753
	Male	25	65,12	7,70		

According to the Table 2, the teachers' coursebook dependency varies only in the sub-dimension "Obligations/Advantages" in favor of males (p=,049), and the variable gender does not affect other sub-dimensions. Table 3 presents data on whether teachers' coursebook dependency varies according to the variable school type.

Table 3: t-Test Results According to the Variable "School Type"

Sub-Dimension	School Type	N	Average	ss	t	p<0,05
Limitations	Private School	19	23,52	4,75	-1,326	,191
	State School	34	25,41	5,07		
Obligations	Private School	19	12,10	2,82	-,509	,613
	State School	34	12,52	2,95		
Activities	Private School	19	22,63	2,92	2,527	,015
	State School	34	20,02	3,91		
Teacher's Competence	Private School	19	5,57	2,03	-1,720	,092
	State School	34	7,23	3,90		
Total	Private School	19	63,84	7,33	-,545	,588
	State School	34	65,20	9,41		

When we look at the table, it is remarkable that there is a significant difference in the sub-dimension activities in favor of the teachers working in private schools. In other sub-dimensions, there is no significant difference according to the variable "school type". Table 4 presents data on the effect of teachers' level of education on their coursebook dependency.

Table 4: t-Test Results According to the Variable “Level of Education”

Sub-Dimension	Level of Education	N	Average	ss	t	p<0,05
Limitations	Undergraduate	47	24,97	5,02	,989	,327
	Graduate	6	25,41	4,79		
Obligations	Undergraduate	47	12,51	2,94	,938	,352
	Graduate	6	11,33	2,33		
Activities	Undergraduate	47	20,82	3,89	-,711	,480
	Graduate	6	22,00	2,68		
Teacher’s Competence	Undergraduate	47	6,85	3,54	1,253	,216
	Graduate	6	5,00	1,67		
Total	Undergraduate	47	65,17	8,89	1,065	,292
	Graduate	6	61,16	6,17		

Based on Table 4, it is seen that teachers’ coursebook dependency does not vary according to their level of education. However, the total average of teachers with an undergraduate degree ($\bar{X}=65,17$) is higher than the average score of teachers with a graduate degree ($\bar{X}=61,16$). Table 5 presents data on the effect of teachers’ years of experience on their coursebook dependency.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance Results According to the Variable “Professional Experience”

Sub-Dimensions	Sources of Variance	Sum Squares	Sd	Mean Squares	F	p<0,05
Limitations	Intergroup	141,043	4	35,261	1,460	,229
	Within Group (error)	1159,259	48	24,151		
	Total	1300,302	52			
Obligations	Intergroup	71,480	4	17,870	2,363	,066
	Within Group (error)	362,972	48	7,562		
	Total	434,453	52			
Activities	Intergroup	83,785	4	20,946	1,528	,209
	Within Group (error)	658,140	48	13,711		
	Total	741,925	52			
Teacher’s Competence	Intergroup	52,489	4	13,122	1,129	,354
	Within Group (error)	557,700	48	11,619		
	Total	610,189	52			
Total	Intergroup	595,440	4	148,860	2,151	,089
	Within Group (error)	3321,315	48	69,194		
	Total	3916,755	52			

According to the table above, it can be stated that teachers’ coursebook dependency does not vary according to their years of experience. However, according to the total average scores (1-5 years=65,90, 6-10 years=67,93, 11-15 years=61,07, 16-20 years=61,63, 21 years and above=73,00), it can be stated that the teachers with 21 years of experience depend on coursebooks most, and the teachers with 11-15 years of experience depend least.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

As a result of the study, which examines Turkish language teachers' coursebook dependency, it is seen that the teachers have a moderate average in the dimensions "limitations and obligations/advantages", an above-average in the dimension "activities", and a below-average in the dimension "teacher's competence". These results show that the teachers depend on coursebooks moderately according to the items in the first and second sub-dimension of the scale; in terms of the items in the sub-dimension "activities" they highly depend on coursebooks; and as for the items in the sub-dimension "teacher's competence", they have a low level of dependency. In other words, the teachers like the activities in the coursebooks and depend on them in this respect. Also, the teachers disagree with the idea that they depend on coursebooks as they do not have enough competencies. Besides, it is seen that there is a significant difference in the sub-dimension "obligations/advantages" in favor of males, and there is a significant difference in the sub-dimension "school type" in favor of teachers working in private schools. It is also seen that the variables "level of education and years of experience" do not have any effect on teachers' coursebook dependency. However, it is understood that the teachers with 21 years of experience depend on coursebooks more, and the teachers with 11-15 years of experience depend on coursebooks less.

When the results are evaluated from another point of view, it is seen that the teachers mostly depend on coursebooks in terms of activities. This fact may signify that the teachers like the activities in coursebooks. The results of the studies that the teachers find the textbooks useful support this data (Kabadayi, 2010; Sahin, 2010). On the other side, considering that the teachers moderately depend on coursebooks in terms of texts in them, it is understood that they do not think positively about the texts. Regarding this fact, Kolac (2003) states that the quality of coursebooks should be improved in every aspect based on teachers' views; Epcacan and Okcu (2010) state that teachers are "undecided" about the adequacy of coursebooks; Aslan and Dogu (2015) state that students do not like the texts in the coursebooks.

According to another result of the study, Turkish Language teachers do not see the insufficiency of their subject matter knowledge as the reason for depending on coursebooks. According to this, it is understood that the teachers see themselves at a good point in terms of their subject matter knowledge. It can be stated that teachers are moderately dependent on coursebooks with a holistic evaluation based on the results. In light of the results, the following suggestions can be presented to researchers who will study in this field and to experts/commissions to prepare coursebooks:

- 1) To increase teachers' dependency on coursebooks, coursebooks should be prepared in a more qualified in line with teachers' views. While doing this, the results of the studies in the literature should be considered.
- 2) This study is limited to the views of teachers working in secondary schools affiliated to Tokat Provincial Directorate of National Education. Turkish Language

teachers' coursebook dependency can be determined within a different and larger sample.

- 3) Qualitative studies can be conducted to determine the reasons affecting Turkish Language teachers' coursebook dependency.

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